

From the Editor

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Greetings to all who question, think, and explore,

It is with great pleasure that we present to you the inaugural issue of the Journal of Culture, Society and Communication (JCSC). The production of scientific knowledge stands as one of the most valuable pillars of humanity's collective legacy. We believe that knowledge should not remain solely at the theoretical level, but should also engage with and influence all aspects of social life.

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Our primary aim is to develop new approaches to understanding and interpreting the communicative actions, cultural dynamics, and lived experiences of society, particularly within the scope of the social sciences and humanities. JCSC is a peer-reviewed journal that centers critical thinking, upholds academic freedom, operates in accordance with universal and ethical values, embraces innovative methods and techniques, supports open access policies, and seeks to enhance the value of scientific knowledge and its production.

In this first issue, we are pleased to share six academic contributions: four research articles, one review article, and one book review. The field of educational sciences is represented by Gökhan Demircioğlu et al. with "Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions of the Concept of Mathematics: A Metaphor Analysis", and by Ay and Elkılıç with "An Analysis of EFL Instructors' Use of Information and Com-

munication Technologies in English Preparatory Classes After the Covid-19 Pandemic". In the field of management, Asiltürk contributes with "What We Have Left From the 2023 Kahramanmaraş Türkiye Earthquake: The Role of Transformational Leadership in Disaster Management and the Importance of Becoming a Sustainable Community in Crisis Management". From the field of advertising, Yığıcı presents "Use of Advertising Appeal in Magazine Advertisements: The Atlas Magazine Example". Additionally, Yörük and Güneş contribute a review article titled "Semiotic Approaches and Strategies in Political Communication", while Sevimli offers a book review titled "A Review of Place Branding: Identity, Image and Reputation Book".

We would like to extend our sincere thanks to all who contributed to the first issue of JCSC, especially the editorial board, publication committee, and advisory board. We are also deeply grateful to the scholars who undertook the peer-review process. The call for papers for the second issue of JCSC will begin in July 2025. We welcome academic contributions in the fields of social sciences, humanities, and educational sciences for our second issue, to be published in December 2025.

Stay connected with science.

Dr. Aytaç Burak DERELİ
JCSC / Publisher and Editor-in-Chief